

Final Report for Agreement NF001

Implementing and Evaluating the Effectiveness of Native Vegetative Buffers at Controlling Nonpoint Source Pollution and as a Tool for Public Education along the Indian River Lagoon

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The overall goal of this project is to determine the effectiveness of living shorelines compared with turf grass dominant sites in the Mosquito Lagoon (ML) and its watershed at decreasing the amount of pollution entering the waterbody from runoff and incorporating private and publicly owned waterfront properties into coastal resilience projects to improve water quality and ameliorate negative impacts of surface runoff.

The project compares living shoreline's and turfgrass shoreline's structural (vegetation) complexity and effectiveness at removing nutrients and suspended solids from surface runoff; establishes and implements means of measuring *in-situ* surface runoff via Simulated Rain Events (SRE); and provides public education to waterfront property owners and other coastal residents. The project consisted of 15 experimental living shorelines, ten sites on the Mosquito Lagoon (ML sites) and five Coastal Retention Pond sites (CRP sites), which were compared against 15 turfgrass control sites (10 ML and 5 CRP sites). Surface water, Simulated Rain Event (SRE) water, and vegetative indices associated with nutrient sequestration were monitored post-construction.

The SRE device was used to replicate surface runoff in the study and was later evaluated on set-up, sample collection, processing, and overall use to assist with future research. Throughout the project, homeowners, city officials and other entities involved in the study were assessed on their personal preferences surrounding living shorelines, native plants, and "Florida- friendly" yard practices. The tools and products can be incorporated with recommendations for others interested in creating living shorelines at public and privately owned waterfront properties.

The analyses of the data found that Total Kjeldahl Nitrogen (TKN) and orthophosphate levels were significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) different between the ML sites and the CRP sites. Vegetation type (living shoreline or turfgrass control sites) was a significant factor for differences based on the vegetation parameters monitored ($P \leq 0.05$). Leaf Area Index (LAI) was found to be significantly different by vegetation type ($P \leq 0.05$), suggesting that the plant canopy structure and complexity of native Florida plants vary when compared against turf grasses. The mean coverage of plants was found to be significantly different by type (control or planted) ($P \leq 0.05$), significantly higher at control sites as control sites were dominated by a dense groundcover of established turfgrass. These results assist with the confirmation that living shorelines' effectiveness is time-dependent and further display the complexities of small-scale residential and public property living shoreline projects.

PROJECT LOCATION AND PROJECT RATIONALE

The Indian River Lagoon (IRL) system has experienced occurrences of severe phytoplankton blooms since 2011, which have been associated with increased nutrient levels stemming from increased amounts of surface water runoff (Bellamy and Cho 2019). Since the 2011 Super algal bloom, the IRL lost over 60% of its seagrasses. Seagrass is an essential component to a healthy estuary and is the food source and/or habitat for many species of marine mammals, fishes, and invertebrates. The IRL receives runoff water from the surrounding urban, suburban and rural areas within the watershed. This runoff and nonpoint source pollution can carry harmful pollutants including fertilizers, pesticides, pet waste, yard debris and other contributors into the ML via stormwater drainage systems. Effective stormwater management is essential in mitigating the sources of nonpoint source pollution to protect its water quality and biological resources.

The project area lies in the northern most sub-lagoon, the Mosquito Lagoon (ML; Fig. 1), with sites in the cities of New Smyrna Beach, Edgewater and Oak Hill displayed in Figure 2. This area of central Florida has an abundance of shoreline properties that allowed the study to take place. The Atlantic Intracoastal Waterway (ICW) runs through Volusia County's eastern coast and provides a shoreline that extends into the ML. The ICW is a man-made channel that was first dredged in 1927 by the Florida Inland Navigation District. In its beginning stages, most of the shorelines were most likely naturally graded shorelines. In contrast, the most predominant shoreline protection strategy used now is hardened shorelines.

Turfgrass shorelines and hardened structures are prevalent throughout the ML. Manicured turfgrass yards are aesthetically pleasing according to American culture and the public norm. In some neighborhoods, they often are mandatory through Homeowners Associations (HOAs).

Figure 1. Map of Mosquito Lagoon The cities of New Smyrna Beach, Edgewater and Oak Hill within Volusia County are all included in the project. The inset map shows the location of Volusia County in relation to the state of Florida.

Figure 2. Locations of living shoreline and control sites of Coastal Retention Ponds (left) and Mosquito Lagoon Shorelines (right) and Coastal Retention Ponds used in the project. Planted sites are depicted in blue circles and control sites are depicted as red circles.

Site Selection

Bethune-Cookman University worked together with partner institutions including the Marine Discovery Center (MDC) and the Florida Department of Environmental Protection (FDEP) Indian River Lagoon Aquatic Preserve to identify twenty (20) waterfront properties bordering the Mosquito Lagoon (ML Shorelines) and ten (10) similarly sized coastal retention ponds (CRPs) within the Mosquito Lagoon watershed. The CRP’s must have had turf grass lawns that extend to ordinary high water level (OHWL which was visually determined at each site) in order to be considered sufficient candidates for a shoreline property to be used within the study. The OHWL is defined as the highest reach of a navigable, *nontidal* water body as it usually exists when in its ordinary condition and is not the highest reach of such water body during the high water season or in times of freshets. Ideal ML sites to be used as controls were to have turf grass lawns that extended to the mean high water level (MHWL).

Property-owners were solicited through mailings, door-to-door visits, newspaper articles/solicitation, as well as public workshops. Soliciting homeowners for their participation

in this project proved a challenging process. Many did not want to disturb their manicured turf grass, nor obstruct their waterfront view with potentially tall, native plants. Others were concerned about the maintenance of the project over the long term. Despite some homeowners' concerns, 30 sites were selected for the study, half were used as controls and allowed to remain as turfgrass lawns (Tables 1 and 2).

Construction of living shorelines for ML sites followed the planting protocols established by FDEP's living shoreline restoration project which has previously been limited to the southern IRL. The CRPs within the project served as another means to monitor and assess native plantings in living shorelines in a controlled and limited setting. The nature of a retention pond would allow for a better understanding of water quality over time as the system is enclosed, freshwater, and was expected to be relatively stable when compared with the entire Mosquito Lagoon system and its water quality.

Table 1. Coastal retention pond sites that were selected for this project, along with GPS coordinates, and estimated pond surface area.

Pond No.	Planted (P)/ Control (C)	GPS Location	Est. Pond Surface Area (m²)	Est. Pond Surface Area (ft²)
CRP01	P	29.015034, -80.974286	724	7,795
CRP02	P	29.015174, -80.938061	372	4,000
CRP03	P	28.993482, -80.904786	581	6,253
CRP04	P	28.966978, -80.920542	785	8,446
CRP05	P	28.919866, -80.883969	1127	12,129
CRP06	C	29.014457, -80.974326	535	5,754
CRP07	C	29.014922, -80.921732	943	10,150
CRP08	C	28.977870, -80.905551	769	8,282
CRP09	C	28.967410, -80.920845	149	1,600
CRP10	C	28.919333, -80.883459	506	5,450

Table 2. Mosquito Lagoon Shoreline locations that were selected for this study and their GPS coordinates.

Site ID	Planted/Control (P/C)	GPS Coordinates
MLS01	P	28.865336, -80.834517
MLS02	P	28.865735, -80.833856
MLS03	P	29.041363, -80.957601
MLS04	P	29.028891, -80.957771
MLS05	P	28.989579, -80.901296
MLS06	P	28.988582, -80.901657
MLS07	P	28.990201, -80.903323
MLS08	P	29.033889, -80.947371
MLS09	P	29.020410, -80.918562
MLS10	P	29.031241, -80.921781
MLS11	C	28.865972, -80.834224
MLS12	C	28.885458, -80.845809
MLS13	C	29.041341, -80.958191
MLS14	C	29.029059, -80.957698
MLS15	C	28.979282, -80.895000
MLS16	C	28.989166, -80.900942
MLS17	C	29.020203, -80.918462
MLS18	C	29.020904, -80.918862
MLS19	C	29.031004, -80.921819
MLS20	C	29.034149, -80.947331

PLANTING DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

Coastal Retention Pond

The 10 ponds selected for the study were varying sizes and shapes. After selecting the ponds to be planted for the project, a 13.3 meter (40 ft) linear shoreline was installed at each of the five experimental sites using Florida native aquatic plants and sand cordgrass.

Plant type and planting zones were determined based on salinity, size of littoral zones, and the contour of ponds. The mean salinity needed to be low (<0.5 ppt) in order to be considered a coastal freshwater pond, though at times these coastal retention ponds had higher salinities due to tidal water influx.

In addition to shoreline littoral zone planting, the five experimental CRP's had a vegetated floating mat installed, known as a BeeMat® (Beeman's BeeMats, 3637 Route 44, New Smyrna Beach, Florida 32168). The floating mat was used in combination with the planted shoreline to assist in sequestering nutrients previously contained in the water column. The floating vegetative mats were 58 m² in size and installed in the center of each planted pond site. Their movement was restricted by installing anchors to the bottom of the pond. The species installed in the floating mats were golden canna (*Canna flaccida*), pickerel weed (*Pontederia cordata*), arrowhead (*Sagittaria lancifolia*), and black needle rush (*Juncus effusus*).

Mosquito Lagoon Shoreline: Planting Design

In order to test the efficiency of living shorelines with native plants at sequestering nutrients from runoff prior to it entering the Mosquito Lagoon, ML shoreline sites were also planted with Florida native plants. The ten experimental ML sites were planted with salt marsh grasses including, *Spartina alterniflora*, *S. patens*, and/or *S. bakeri*. The shorelines were planted along a 13.3 m section adjacent to the lagoon. The width of the plantings extended from 2 m up to 5 m from near mean low water level. The width of the plantings depended on the slope and shape of the shoreline. All plants were installed as 1-quart specimens at 0.3 m (1-ft) centers.

MONITORING

In order to test the nutrient buffering capabilities of living shorelines versus turf grass lawns, a total of fifteen (15) experimental living shorelines were established consisting of ten (10) lagoon shorelines and five (5) coastal retention pond shorelines, along with fifteen (15) predominately turf grass control sites to compare the surface water, ground water, soil, and vegetative indices associated with nutrient and carbon storage.

Living shorelines constructed along the ML were monitored based on the sampling schedule (Table 3) presented in the approved Quality Assurance Project Plan (QAPP). However, the actual sampling dates were adjusted due to conditions of weather, hurricanes, and other logistics that are conventional to the nature of field work.

Table 3. The original timeline of sampling events for 5 sample sets, SRE (simulated rain event) water sample, surface water sample, ground water sample, soil sample, and vegetation sample. Parameters analyzed are also listed for each sample set. Green checks denote the parameters analyzed for each sampling period (Q1-Q4) and red cross-marks denote the parameters not analyzed for given sampling period.

Year		2017 (year 1 sampling)	2018 (year 2 sampling)				2019 (year 3 sampling)			
Sampling Period		Pre-Sample/Yr1	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
Parameter ↓ / Month →		Jun-Nov	Dec-Feb	Mar-May	Jun-Aug	Sep-Nov	Dec-Feb	Mar-May	Jun-Aug	Sep-Nov
SRE Water Sample*	Total Kjeldahl Nitrogen	✓	×	×	✓	×	×	×	✓	
	Total Kjeldahl Phosphorus	✓	×	×	✓	×	×	×	✓	
	Ammonia	✓	×	×	✓	×	×	×	✓	
	Nitrate	✓	×	×	✓	×	×	×	✓	
	Orthophosphate	✓	×	×	✓	×	×	×	✓	
	pH	✓	×	×	✓	×	×	×	✓	
	TSS	✓	×	×	✓	×	×	×	✓	
Surface Water Sample	Total Kjeldahl Nitrogen	✓	×	×	✓	×	×	×	✓	
	Total Kjeldahl Phosphorus	✓	×	×	✓	×	×	×	✓	
	Ammonia	✓	×	×	✓	×	×	×	✓	
	Nitrate	✓	×	×	✓	×	×	×	✓	
	Orthophosphate	✓	×	×	✓	×	×	×	✓	
	pH	✓	×	×	✓	×	×	×	✓	
	TSS	✓	×	×	✓	×	×	×	✓	
	Temperature (field)	✓	×	×	✓	×	×	×	✓	
	Salinity (field)	✓	×	×	✓	×	×	×	✓	
	pH (field)	✓	×	×	✓	×	×	×	✓	
DO (field)	✓	×	×	✓	×	×	×	✓		
Ground Water	Total Kjeldahl Nitrogen	✓	×	×	✓	×	×	×	✓	
	Total Kjeldahl Phosphorus	✓	×	×	✓	×	×	×	✓	
	Ammonia	✓	×	×	✓	×	×	×	✓	
	Nitrate	✓	×	×	✓	×	×	×	✓	
	Orthophosphate	✓	×	×	✓	×	×	×	✓	
	pH	✓	×	×	✓	×	×	×	✓	

Soil	TSS	✓	×	×	✓	×	×	×	✓
	soil moisture	✓	×	×	✓	×	×	×	✓
	soil temperature	✓	×	×	✓	×	×	×	✓
Vegetation	Leaf Area Index	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	vegetative cover (% cover)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	average vegetative height	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	Vegetative turnover	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	Standing crop marsh	✓	×	×	✓	×	×	×	✓
	standing crop turf	✓	×	×	✓	×	×	×	✓
	standing crop pond shore	✓	×	×	✓	×	×	×	✓
	standing crop floating mats	✓	×	×	✓	×	×	×	✓
	Slope	✓	×	×	×	×	×	×	✓

†SRE water sample will be composited in after collection.

- Below is a list of the actual sampling dates for each respective quarter between Q3 – 2017 to Q4 – 2019. (**Bold items = Full SRE-Simulated Rain Event- sampling**)
 - **Q3- 2017 August 30th – November 17th, 2017 (Pre-Sample/Yr1)**
 - Q4- 2017 December 4th – December 12th, 2017
 - Q1- 2018 March 6th – March 7th, 2018
 - Q2- 2018 June 4th – June 12th, 2018
 - **Q3- 2018 September 9th – November 5th, 2018**
 - Q1- 2019 January 29th – March 4th, 2019
 - Q2- 2019 May 9th – 15th, 2019
 - **Q3- 2019 July 30th – September 27th, 2019**
 - Q4- 2019 January 28th – May 23rd, 2020 (Extra, not listed in QAPP)

Descriptions on monitoring, sampling, laboratory/field measurements, as well as data analyses are also in the QAPP document.

Simulated Rain Event (SRE)

The design of the SRE utilized in this project varied due to constraints of the project design, including high slope of various waterfront shorelines, maneuverability, and transportation. The SRE design used by the Bethune- Cookman Laboratory staff is displayed in Figure 3.

The overall design is consistent with the Humphrey et al. (2002) design, however, the collection method used in this project differed due to the use of privately-owned lots and the need to constantly move the device. In this project, the metal plot was laid on the top of the soil and hammered into place. Instead of water being allowed to infiltrate the soil and flow out as sub-surface water, the SRE water was allowed to pool at the bottom of the surface runoff plot and collected via a syringe.

Throughout the course of the project, notes were taken on the set-up, take down, maintenance, usability, sample collection and processing, and overall use of the SRE design. These field notes, laboratory statements, and results from in-situ use of the SRE were used to identify factors that

can help improve future use of the SRE and other tools to help understand surface runoff collection methods.

Figure 3. Simulated Rain Event structure in use during sampling event.

Surface Water Sampling

Surface water sampling was conducted using a Nalgene 500 ml bottle from the surface. The bottles were pre-labeled with pre-printed waterproof labels to identify each sample. Ground water samples were not taken as sites did not have available wells. Time, costs, and homeowner preference limited the availability to install wells for ground water sampling.

Surface Water Analyses

Surface water samples were analyzed *in situ*, in the BCU laboratory, and in an offsite laboratory. The variables that were measured *in situ* using a YSI ProDSS (YSI Inc. / Xylem Inc., 1725 Brannum Lane, Yellow Springs, Ohio 45387) instrument were calibrated with KCl solution before daily use. The *in situ* measurements include temperature, salinity, pH, and dissolved oxygen following EPA methods and protocols. The variables measured in an offsite laboratory include total kjeldahl nitrogen (TKN), total kjeldahl phosphorus (TKP), ammonia, nitrate, orthophosphate, pH, total suspended solids (TSS), and percent of organic solids suspended. TKN and TKP were determined using the Ion Selective Electrode and following the EPA methodology at an outsourced laboratory in Escambia County (Escambia County Water Quality Laboratory, 3363 West Park Place, Pensacola, Florida 32505).

Soil Sampling

The coring apparatus (corer) was constructed using PVC tubes, specifically, 2-inch (5.08 cm) diameter schedule 40 PVC. A 35-cm-long PVC pipe will be fitted with a socket-to-threaded fitting at one end and sealed with a threaded end cap. The corer was pushed into the soil using a rubber mallet with the cap removed. Once in place, the cap was placed on the corer; and the soil sample extracted. Once extracted the open end of the corer was capped with a socket PVC cap, the sample was appropriately labeled, and stored in a cooler with frozen gel packs or ice until transported to the laboratory.

The soil samples taken before and after the SRE plot were taken to the BCU WQ Laboratory to be weighed and dried to gain the dry weight. This measurement provides information on moisture content pre- and post- SRE and the potential amount of moisture that a given soil can retain before surface runoff is released.

Vegetation measures for organic content in plant biomass

To assess vegetative parameters (canopy height, leaf area index, standing crop and plant cover), transects were laid out in line with the randomly selected SRE plots. The transects encompassed the 1m² SRE plot and ran from the mean high-water mark to the topmost planted zone at a perpendicular angle to the shoreline at the transects location. Prior to the SRE and within the defined transect, the height of the tallest plant in each species zone was recorded using a 2m ruled stick to determine the maximum height of each species. Each of the tallest plant species was measured three times to reduce human error. To determine the average canopy height of each zone, 10 haphazard measurements were taken in each zone using the 2m stick. Leaf Area Index (LAI) was calculated by measuring Photosynthetically Active Radiation (PAR) at the top and the bottom of the canopy on various species. The PAR measurements were collected with a LI-COR LI-250A light sensor and meter. The Beer-Lambert extinction law was used to calculate LAI

of the given plant canopies. Haphazardly within a transect, a light meter reading was taken over a given area of plants, and a paired value was taken directly underneath the canopy. Five pairs of readings were taken for each vegetation zone.

The short-mowed nature of turf grass presents a challenge for taking light measurements. Due to the short height of the turf grass vegetation, the below-canopy radiation measurement was not possible in many cases and almost always nearly reflected the incident radiation value.

The Beer-Lambert equation method for LAI requires measurements of both incident at the canopy top (I_0) and below-canopy radiation (I) along with an extinction coefficient (k).

The plant standing crops for all sites were measured at the end of the project. Standing crop biomass was collected at 3 randomly selected plots per site. The 1m × 1m plots were divided into 4 equal quarters and one of the four quarters (0.5 m × 0.5 m) were randomly sampled by means of random number generation. All above ground growth was sampled by clipping at the soil level.

To determine plant cover, a 1m × 1m PVC quadrat with 100-10 cm² grids was placed over the plot. The presence of rooted vegetation in each 10 cm² section was counted for each plant species. The percent coverage method was based on the Braun-Blanquet cover/abundance scale recommended by the National Resource Research Institute for plant coverage sampling and is the Standard Relve for emergent vegetation. By this method, the percent coverage for a species of plant was assigned a cover class rather than determining an exact percent cover.

ANALYSES AND RESULT SUMMARY

Annual Sampling (SRE, SWL, SWF, Vegetation)

The Simulated Rain Event (SRE) sample set ANOVAR results:

Table 4. Simulated Rain Event (SRE) Sample Set: ANOVARS Lagoon and Pond (TKN, TKP, TSS, Nitrate, Orthophosphate)

Independent Variables	Dependent Variables	Lagoon			Pond		
		F	d.f.	P	F	d.f.	P
Vegetation Type	Total Kjeldahl Nitrogen	0.02508	1	0.0234	0.4861	1	0.4570
Time		0.93717	2	0.9382	0.6287	2	0.6152
Vegetation Type × Time		0.49095	2	0.4954	0.6480	2	0.6260
		F	d.f.	P	F	d.f.	P
Vegetation Type	Total Kjeldahl Phosphorus	0.1033	1	0.1042	0.6081	1	0.6139
Time		0.6122	2	0.6232	0.5430	2	0.4942
Vegetation Type × Time		0.3964	2	0.3992	0.6880	2	0.6678

			<i>F</i>	<i>d.f.</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>d.f.</i>	<i>P</i>
Vegetation Type			0.5058	1	0.5776	0.46663	1	0.4762
Time	Total Suspended Solids		0.3911	2	0.4358	0.07564	2	0.0642
Vegetation Type × Time			0.3175	2	0.3620	0.13033	2	0.1080
			<i>F</i>	<i>d.f.</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>d.f.</i>	<i>P</i>
Vegetation Type			0.67668	1	0.7222	0.783802	1	0.7838
Time	Ammonia		0.01106	2	0.0070	0.024759	2	0.0242
Vegetation Type × Time			0.52353	2	0.5722	0.001559	2	0.0018
			<i>F</i>	<i>d.f.</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>d.f.</i>	<i>P</i>
Vegetation Type			0.67915	1	0.6818	0.3515	1	0.2766
Time	Nitrate		0.09819	2	0.0918	0.3008	2	0.2006
Vegetation Type × Time			0.44583	2	0.4596	0.2995	2	0.2026
			<i>F</i>	<i>d.f.</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>d.f.</i>	<i>P</i>
Vegetation Type			0.02244	1	0.0248	0.5555	1	0.5758
Time	Orthophosphate		0.09595	2	0.0906	0.8633	2	0.8788
Vegetation Type × Time			0.19384	2	0.1842	0.7807	2	0.8040

Both TKN and Orthophosphate were found to be significantly different at lagoon sites by vegetation type (Living Shorelines (planted) vs. turfgrass), but not by sampling time or the interaction of time and vegetation type. Neither the pond TKN nor orthophosphate was significantly different by vegetation type, time, nor the interaction of the two factors.

Time and the two-way interaction of vegetation type and time had a significant effect on ammonia at pond sites. (Table 4)

Annual TKP, TSS and Nitrate were not significantly different at both lagoon and pond sites by vegetation type, time, nor the interaction between time and vegetation type.

Annual Simulated Rain Event (SRE) water quality sample results (TKN, TKP, TSS, Ammonia, Nitrate, Orthophosphate) are presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4 Simulated Rain Event Sample Set Annual Means and SD Measurements (Total Kjeldahl Nitrogen (TKN), Total Kjeldahl Phosphorus (TKP), Total Suspended Solids (TSS), Ammonia, Nitrate, Orthophosphate) for Lagoon and Pond planted and control sites. Light green circles depict CRP control sites; Dark green circles depict CRP planted sites; Light blue squares depict MLS control sites, Dark blue squares depict MLS planted sites.

TKN concentrations within lagoon planted and control sites did not change significantly over time in value from 2017 through 2019. At planted sites, the value ranged 9.4 - 13.8 mg N/m², but the control sites displayed higher TKN values than planted sites (within the ML sties), with mean concentrations ranging 22.7 - 28.6 mg N/m² (Fig. 4A).

TKN measurements within retention pond planted sites did not change significantly from 2017-2019, with mean concentrations ranging from 6.2 - 12.8 mg N/m², however control retention pond sites displayed fluctuating TKN values each year, increasing substantially in 2018 ($\approx 101 \pm 81$ mg N/m²) and decreasing in 2019 ($\approx 28.1 \pm 18.0$ mg N/m²). This increase in TKN concentration and standard deviation within the group may have been due to a particular control pond site (CRP-10) with substantially higher TKN concentrations than the remaining lagoon control sites (Fig. 4B).

Mean SRE-TKP concentrations within lagoon planted sites decreased reaching a minimum concentration of 1.6 ± 0.4 mg N/m² in 2019, while concentrations at lagoon control sites decreased in 2018 ($\approx 3.3 \pm 0.6$ mg N/m²) and increased in 2019 (4.8 ± 1.8 mg N/m²) (Fig. 4B).

TKP concentrations at retention pond sites displayed similar patterns as lagoon sites, where concentrations at planted sites slightly decreased each year, reaching a minimum mean concentration of 0.6 ± 0.3 mg N/m² in 2019, while concentrations at lagoon control sites in 2018 increased ($\approx 3.3 \pm 0.6$ mg N/m²) and decreased in 2019 ($\approx 3.8 \pm 2.7$ mg N/m²) (Fig. 4B).

Ammonia concentrations showed similar patterns for both lagoon planted and control sites. Planted sites increased in concentration in 2018 ($\approx 1.0 \pm 0.1$ mg N/m²) and decreased slightly in 2019 ($\approx 0.8 \pm 0.3$ mg N/m²), while control sites increased concentration in 2018 ($\approx 1.1 \pm 0.1$ mg N/m²) and decreased to similar concentrations from 2017 sampling in 2019 ($\approx 0.6 \pm 0.1$ mg N/m²) (Fig. 4C).

Ammonia concentrations at retention pond sites also fluctuated each year, however ranges in mean concentrations at planted sites were less variable (0.6 – 0.8 mg/L) than pond control sites (0.3 - 1.2 mg/L) (Fig. 4C).

Nitrate concentrations fluctuated at lagoon planted sites ranging from approximately 0.1 – 0.8 m/L. Nitrate concentrations substantially increased in 2018, which caused the increase in deviation and range at lagoon planted sites. This may have been due to a particular planted site (MLS-02) displaying substantially higher nitrate concentrations than the remaining sites. Nitrate concentrations decreased each year at control sites, mean concentrations ranging from approximately 0.1 – 0.6 m/L (Fig. 4D).

Nitrate concentrations at planted retention pond sites increase each year reaching a maximum mean concentration of 0.6 ± 0.0 mg/L in 2019. However, the control sites' nitrate concentrations remained consistent from 2017 through 2019, mean concentrations ranging from approximately 0.1 – 0.2 mg/L (Fig. 4D).

Orthophosphate concentrations at lagoon planted sites remained consistent from 2017 to 2019, ranging from 0.6 – 0.7 mg/L. Concentrations fluctuated at lagoon control sites throughout the three-year sampling period, however displayed higher orthophosphate concentrations, mean concentrations ranging from 0.9 – 1.4 mg/L. One particular control site (MLS-02) had substantially higher orthophosphate concentrations than the other control sites (Fig. 4E)

Concentrations of orthophosphate at planted pond sites fluctuated from 2017 to 2019, ranging from 0.6 – 0.8 mg/L with high variance within the group sample. Control pond sites also displayed fluctuating orthophosphate measurements (ranging from 0.4 – 0.7 mg/L), however exhibited lower variance within the group sample than the pond planted sites (Fig. 4E).

Total suspended solid measurements at both lagoon planted and control sites fluctuated each year. At planted sites, mean TSS concentrations ranged from 442.4 – 778.0 mg/L, while mean TSS values at control sites ranged from 495.6 – 1298.2 mg/L. One particular control site (MLS-02) had substantially higher TSS concentrations than the remaining control sites (Fig. 4F).

At pond sites, total suspended solid measurements at planted sites increased in value each year, mean concentrations ranging from approximately 204.3 – 1366.7 mg/L from 2017 to 2019. However, TSS measurements at control sites displayed a different trend fluctuating each year, substantially increasing in 2018 ($\approx 826.0 \pm 445.7$) and decreasing in 2019 ($\approx 427.2 \pm 157.3$) (Fig. 4F).

The annual surface water sample lab measurements ANOVAR results:

Neither vegetation type, time, nor the interaction between the two factors play a significant role in the effects of the lab surface water variables measured at both lagoon and pond sites ($p > 0.05$) (Table 5).

Table 5. Annual Lab Surface Water (SWL) Sample Set: ANOVARS Lagoon and Pond (TKN, TKP, TSS, Nitrate, Orthophosphate)

Independent Variables	Dependent Variables	Lagoon			Pond		
		F	d.f.	P	F	d.f.	P
Vegetation Type	Total	0.6695	1	0.6734	0.8468	1	0.8742
Time	Kjeldahl	0.0898	2	0.0936	0.6269	2	0.6926
Vegetation Type × Time	Nitrogen	0.8644	2	0.8652	0.5975	2	0.6496
		F	d.f.	P	F	d.f.	P
Vegetation Type	Total	0.96642	1	0.9704	0.6177	1	0.7460
Time	Kjeldahl	0.07817	2	0.0796	0.6260	2	0.7452
Vegetation Type × Time	Phosphorus	0.11264	2	0.1150	0.4798	2	0.5638
		F	d.f.	P	F	d.f.	P

Vegetation Type		0.6829	1	0.6418	0.7265	1	0.8058
Time	Total Suspended Solids	0.5045	2	0.5352	0.5281	2	0.6010
Vegetation Type × Time		0.2346	2	0.2732	0.3046	2	0.3076
		F	d.f.	P	F	d.f.	P
Vegetation Type		0.9785	1	0.9710	0.2032	1	0.2352
Time	Ammonia	0.5179	2	0.5588	0.5105	2	0.5472
Vegetation Type × Time		0.2772	2	0.3324	0.7921	2	0.8396
		F	d.f.	P	F	d.f.	P
Vegetation Type		0.4636	1	0.6682	0.3866	1	0.2840
Time	Nitrate	0.7935	2	0.9708	0.5802	2	0.5296
Vegetation Type × Time		0.5507	2	0.7640	0.5802	2	0.5316
		F	d.f.	P	F	d.f.	P
Vegetation Type		0.5423	1	0.5518	0.9191	1	0.8976
Time	Orthophosphate	0.7372	2	0.7580	0.7839	2	0.8580
Vegetation Type × Time		0.4459	2	0.4734	0.4034	2	0.4766

The in situ surface water sample set ANOVAR results:

Annual surface water temperature and pH changed significantly throughout the sampling period at lagoon sites. Salinity was significantly different between vegetation type at pond sites because some ponds were close to the lagoon and had brackish salinities with vegetation that tolerates the salts (Table 6).

Table 6. Field Surface Water (SWF) Sample Set: ANOVARS Lagoon and Pond (Temperature, Dissolved Oxygen Concentration and Percent Saturation, Salinity, and pH)

Independent Variables	Dependent Variables	Lagoon			Pond		
		F	d.f.	P	F	d.f.	P
Vegetation Type		6.407e-01	1	0.6424	0.17758	1	0.1688
Time	Temperature	8.122e-08	2	0.0002	0.08266	2	0.0732
Vegetation Type × Time		7.499e-01	2	0.7476	0.08817	2	0.0906
		F	d.f.	P	F	d.f.	P
Vegetation Type		0.6814	1	0.6838	0.37186	1	0.3780
Time	Dissolved Oxygen (mg)	0.2931	2	0.2896	0.08741	2	0.0926
Vegetation Type × Time		0.9086	2	0.9168	0.78620	2	0.7942
		F	d.f.	P	F	d.f.	P

Vegetation Type		0.6927	1	0.6926			
Time	Dissolved Oxygen (%)	0.2212	2	0.2142	"Error in storage mode of a factor"		
Vegetation Type × Time		0.8917	2	0.8976			
		<i>F</i>	<i>d.f.</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>d.f.</i>	<i>P</i>
Vegetation Type		0.91749	1	0.9200	0.02569	1	0.0296
Time	Salinity	0.06407	2	0.0660	0.30482	2	0.3186
Vegetation Type × Time		0.24633	2	0.2432	0.48537	2	0.4794
		<i>F</i>	<i>d.f.</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>d.f.</i>	<i>P</i>
Vegetation Type		6.487e-01	1	0.6424	0.95841	1	0.9588
Time	pH	3.553e-15	2	0.0002	0.05472	2	0.0590
Vegetation Type × Time		8.342e-01	2	0.8392	0.27788	2	0.0590

Figure 5 Field Surface Water Annual Means and SD Measurements (Salinity, Temperature, Dissolved Oxygen (DO), Dissolved Oxygen (%), pH) for Lagoon and Pond sites.

Light green circles depict CRP control sites; Dark green circles depict CRP planted sites; Light blue squares depict MLS control sites; Dark blue squares depict MLS planted sites.

Lagoon site salinity ranged from approximately 17 - 29 ppt (Fig. 5A), corresponding to the natural conditions of the Mosquito Lagoon. Lagoon site salinity stayed within freshwater (<0.5) to brackish levels lower than about 3.6 ppt from 2017 to 2019 (Fig. 5A). A pond site in close

proximity to brackish water inputs from the Mosquito Lagoon (CRP03) had brackish salinity conditions.

All lagoon and pond planted and control sites within the project area show similar trends in temperature ranges throughout the years of 2017 and 2020. The water temperature at each of the sites ranged from approximately 17°C to as high as approximately 30°C depending on seasonal temperature changes during the course of the year (Fig. 5B).

pH measurements displayed similar annual trends at the lagoon sites, ranging from 7.4 - 8.6 throughout the sampling period (Fig. 5C). The pH levels at pond sites ranged from 7.1 - 9.3 throughout the sampling period.

DO concentrations remained relatively stable at the sites located along the Mosquito Lagoon, ranging from approximately 4.5 - 6.5 mg/L (Fig. 5D). Pond planted and control sites also showed similar DO concentrations from 2017 to 2019, both ranging from approximately 4 - 10 mg/L.

DO saturation varied widely at lagoon planted and control sites throughout the sampling period. However, both all sites ranged from approximately 65 - 100% saturation from 2017 to 2019 (Fig. 5E).

The vegetation sample set ANOVAR results:

Tallest vegetation measurements were found to be significantly different at lagoon sites by vegetation type, time, and the interaction of time and vegetation type. At pond sites, tallest vegetation replicates were found to be significantly different by vegetation type, and interaction of time and vegetation type, however not significantly different by time (Table 7).

Average plant height was found to be significantly different at both lagoon and pond sites by vegetation type, time, and the interaction between the time and vegetation type.

Percent vegetation coverage at lagoon sites were found to be significantly different by vegetation type and time, but not the interaction of time and vegetation type. At pond sites, percent vegetation coverage shows significance by vegetation type, however not by time nor the interaction of time and vegetation type (Table 7).

Table 7. Vegetation Sample Set: ANOVARS for Lagoon and Pond Sites (Tallest Vegetation Height, Average Vegetation Height)

Independent Variables	Dependent Variables	Lagoon			Pond		
		F	d.f.	P	F	d.f.	P
Vegetation Type	Tallest Vegetation Height (Rep)	2.881e-11	1	0.0002	0.001304	1	0.0024

	Time		1.652e-03	2	0.0016	0.202727	2	0.2148
	Vegetation Type × Time		1.325e-03	2	0.0010	0.017636	2	0.0152
<hr/>								
	Vegetation Type		9.217e-10	1	0.0002	0.0001297	1	0.0002
	Time	Average Vegetation Height	4.792e-03	2	0.0032	0.0427998	2	0.0412
	Vegetation Type × Time		1.116e-02	2	0.0114	0.0053023	2	0.0030
<hr/>								
	Vegetation Type		1.127e-05	1	0.0002	0.02518	1	0.0262
	Time	Percent Coverage	8.867e-03	2	0.0098	0.06732	2	0.0666
	Vegetation Type × Time		6.466e-02	2	0.0640	0.31574	2	0.3120

Figure 6 Vegetation Sample Set Annual Means and SD Measurements (Average Vegetation Height, and Percent Coverage) for Lagoon and Pond Sites. Light green circles depict CRP control sites; Dark green circles depict CRP planted sites; Light blue squares depict MLS control sites; Dark blue squares depict MLS planted sites.

Vegetation cover at planted (living shorelines) lagoon sites ranged from 58.3 - 73.9% coverage. The slight decrease in percent coverage in 2018 ($\approx 58.3 \pm 5.5\%$) may have been due to the loss by Hurricane Michael, however the mean cover recovered in 2019 ($\approx 73.9 \pm 10.2\%$ coverage) (Fig. 6A). Control lagoon sites remained consistent as well throughout the sampling period, however displaying significantly higher coverage than planted lagoon sites, with average percent coverage ranging from 86.7 - 97.4% coverage. Vegetation cover at planted pond sites also displayed a slight decrease in 2018 due to Hurricane Michael ($\approx 39.6 \pm 10.2\%$) and recovered in 2019 ($\approx 65 \pm 8.4\%$). Control pond sites percent coverage increased with time, increasing from the mean percent

coverage of $50.6 \pm 14.1\%$ in 2017 to $90.4 \pm 3.8\%$ in 2019. It was observed that residents increased lawn maintenance on their turf grass shorelines (Fig. 6A).

Mean vegetation height at lagoon planted sites increased with time throughout the sampling period, increasing from the mean height of 65.5 ± 4.53 cm in 2017 to 98.7 ± 5.1 cm in 2019. However, turf grass average height at control lagoon sites remained consistent throughout the sampling period and displayed substantially lower heights compared to lagoon site measurements (mean control vegetation height of 14 ± 4 cm throughout entire project) (Fig. 6B).

Planted pond sites displayed slight fluctuations in average vegetation height throughout the sampling period. Planted pond sites were impacted by the effects of Hurricane Michael (relatively more than lagoon planted sites), which caused a decrease in average plant height in 2018 (108.8 ± 10.7 cm), however recovered in 2019 (108.8 ± 7.6 cm) (Fig. 6B)

Figure 7. Leaf Area Index (LAI) for Lagoon and Pond Sites.

Leaf area index (LAI) was higher and fluctuated seasonally at planted (living shorelines) sites and remained lower and more stable throughout the season at the control sites. It is because the dominant plants at the control sites are turfgrass which is mowed down regularly.

Quarterly Monitoring (SWF, Vegetation)

The quarterly lab surface water sample set ANOVAR results:

Surface water temperature for both lagoon and pond sites displayed significantly different values by time at lagoon sites. Dissolved oxygen (mg/L) displayed significant results by time at lagoon sites (Table 8; Fig. 9). Salinity was not found to be significantly different by vegetation type, time, nor the interaction of the two (Table 8; Fig. 9). pH was found to be significantly different by time for both lagoon sites and pond sites, however was not significantly affected by vegetation type and the interaction of time and vegetation type (Table 8; Fig. 9).

Table 8. Field surface Water Quality Sample Set: Quarterly ANOVAS Lagoon and Pond (Temperature, Dissolved Oxygen Concentration and Percent Saturation, Salinity, and pH)

Independent Variables	Dependent Variables	Lagoon			Pond		
		F	d.f.	P	F	d.f.	P
Vegetation Type		0.5764859	1	0.5766	0.16666	1	0.1718
Time	Temperature	0.0003352	2	0.0006	0.01286	2	0.0140
Vegetation Type × Time		0.4731858	2	0.4750	0.54890	2	0.5392
		F	d.f.	P	F	d.f.	P
Vegetation Type		0.862352	1	0.8600	0.5807	1	0.7892
Time	Dissolved Oxygen (mg)	0.009798	2	0.0110	0.4723	2	0.5922
Vegetation Type × Time		0.876673	2	0.8726	0.4034	2	0.4386
		F	d.f.	P	F	d.f.	P
Vegetation Type		0.6208	1	0.6236	0.4382	1	0.4418
Time	Dissolved Oxygen (%)	0.3211	2	0.3274	0.4487	2	0.4434
Vegetation Type × Time		0.4142	2	0.4160	0.7833	2	0.7864
		F	d.f.	P	F	d.f.	P
Vegetation Type		0.9626	1	0.9632	0.4382	1	0.4418
Time	Salinity	0.5603	2	0.5502	0.4487	2	0.4434
Vegetation Type × Time		0.7143	2	0.7096	0.7833	2	0.7864
		F	d.f.	P	F	d.f.	P
Vegetation Type		7.970e-01	1	0.7988	0.96053	1	0.9620
Time	pH	1.887e-15	2	0.0002	0.00421	2	0.0050
Vegetation Type × Time		5.714e-01	2	0.5658	0.28751	2	0.2892

Figure 8. Field Surface Water Quarterly Means and SD Measurements (Salinity, Temperature, Dissolved Oxygen (DO), Dissolved Oxygen (%), pH) for Lagoon and Pond planted and control sites. Q4- 2018 nulled due to Hurricane Michael.

The quarterly vegetation sample set:

Tallest vegetation measurements were found to be significantly different at lagoon sites by vegetation type, time, and the interaction of time and vegetation type. At pond sites, tallest vegetation values were found to be significantly different by vegetation type, however was not significantly affected by time nor the interaction of time and vegetation type (Table 9; Fig. 9A).

Average plant height was found to be significantly different at lagoon sites by vegetation type, time, and the interaction of time and vegetation type. At pond sites, average plant height was found to be significantly different by vegetation type, however was not significantly affected by time nor the interaction of time and vegetation type (Table 9; Fig. 9C).

Percent vegetation coverage at lagoon sites were found to be significantly different by vegetation type and time, however the interaction of time and vegetation type had less of an effect on plant coverage (Table 9; Fig. 9B). At pond sites, percent vegetation coverage was not found to be significantly different by vegetation type, time nor the interaction of time and vegetation type (Table 9; Fig. 9B).

Table 9 Vegetation Sample Set: ANOVARS for Lagoon and Pond Sites (Tallest Vegetation Height, Average Vegetation Height)

	Lagoon	Pond
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Independent Variables	Dependent Variables	F	d.f.	P	F	d.f.	P
Vegetation Type	Tallest Vegetation Height (Rep)	2.144e-09	1	0.0002	0.0001051	1	0.0002
Time		1.150e-02	2	0.0120	0.6875660	2	0.6936
Vegetation Type × Time		1.354e-03	2	0.0010	0.4295634	2	0.4266
		F	d.f.	P	F	d.f.	P
Vegetation Type	Average Vegetation Height	4.547e-08	1	0.0002	1.971e-05	1	0.0002
Time		2.566e-03	2	0.0038	4.801e-01	2	0.4750
Vegetation Type × Time		5.714e-04	2	0.0012	2.711e-01	2	0.2758
		F	d.f.	P	F	d.f.	P
Vegetation Type	Percent Coverage	7.232e-05	1	0.0002	0.13172	1	0.1366
Time		5.403e-02	2	0.0486	0.06862	2	0.0682
Vegetation Type × Time		1.299e-01	2	0.1238	0.22070	2	0.2286

Figure 9 Vegetation Sample Set Quarterly Means and SD Measurements (Tallest Vegetation Height, Average Vegetation Height, and Percent Coverage) for Lagoon and Pond Sites

Mean of tallest vegetation heights at planted lagoon sites increased with time throughout the sampling period, increasing from the mean height of 71.9 ± 12.1 cm in 2017 to 105.2 ± 38.5 cm in 2019. From Q3-2017 - Q2-2018, tallest plant height measurements increased, reaching approximately 116.33 ± 10.80 cm in height. However, tallest plant height drastically dropped during Q3-2018 which may be due to the effects of hurricanes. After Hurricane Michael, tallest vegetation measurements at planted pond sites increased throughout the year of 2019. Mean tallest vegetation height at both lagoon and pond control sites remained consistent throughout the sampling period ranging from approximately 10 - 25 cm, substantially lower heights than planted sites, expected when comparing manicured turf grass lawns to natural wetland emergent plants. 2017 control pond vegetation measurements included non-turf grass plants that were present in some of the project participants' waterfront lawns. These observations were noted as miscellaneous vegetation and mostly included weeds (Fig. 9A).

Vegetation cover at planted lagoon sites remained relatively consistent throughout the sampling period with a slight decrease in 2018. Average percent coverage ranged from 58.3 - 73.9% coverage. The decrease in percent coverage in 2018 may have been affected by Hurricane Michael ($\approx 58.3 \pm 5.5\%$), however recovered in 2019 ($\approx 73.9 \pm 10.2\%$ coverage). Control lagoon sites remained consistent as well throughout the sampling period, however displaying significantly higher coverage than planted lagoon sites, with average percent coverage ranging from 86.7 - 97.4% coverage (Fig. 9B).

Vegetation cover at planted pond sites also displayed a slight decrease in 2018 due to Hurricane Michael ($\approx 39.6 \pm 10.2\%$) and recovered in 2019 ($\approx 65 \pm 8.4\%$). Control pond sites percent coverage increased with time, increasing from the mean percent coverage of $50.6 \pm 14.1\%$ in 2017 to $90.4 \pm 3.8\%$ in 2019. It was observed that residents increased the frequency of lawn maintenance on their turf grass shorelines (Fig. 9B)

Mean vegetation height at lagoon planted sites increased with time throughout the sampling period, increasing from the mean height of 65.5 ± 4.5 cm in 2017 to 98.7 ± 5.1 cm in 2019. However, turf grass average height at control lagoon sites remained consistent throughout the sampling period and displayed substantially lower heights compared to lagoon site measurements (mean control vegetation height of 14 ± 4 cm throughout entire project) (Fig. 9C).

Planted pond sites displayed more fluctuations in average vegetation height throughout the sampling period. Plant pond sites were impacted by the effects of Hurricane Michael (relatively more than lagoon planted sites), which caused a decrease in average plant height in 2018 (108.8 ± 10.7 cm), however recovered in 2019 (108.8 ± 7.6 cm) (Fig. 9C).

The annual soil sample set:

Figure 10. Soil Sample Set Annual Means and SE Measurements (pre-SRE Soil Moisture (%) and Temperature, and pose-SRE Soil Moisture (%) and Temperature) for Lagoon and Pond Sites. Light green circles depict CRP control sites; Dark green circles depict CRP planted sites; Light blue squares depict MLS control sites; Dark blue squares depict MLS planted sites.

In 2019, planted lagoon sites gained approximately $7.2 \pm 5.0\%$ soil moisture after utilizing the SRE apparatus, while control sites gained approximately $11.4 \pm 3.6\%$. Planted pond sites gained substantially higher moisture gains after utilizing the SRE when compared to 2017 measurements, which approximated to $11.9 \pm 4.0\%$. Control pond sites however gained less in soil moisture after SRE application when compared to 2017 observations (approximately $2.15 \pm 4.5\%$) (Fig. 10A and B)

Pre-SRE soil temperatures at lagoon sites were significantly lower than soil temperature at pond sites in 2017. In 2017, planted and control lagoon pre-SRE soil temperature ranged from approximately 26 - 27 °C, while planted and control pond sites ranged from approximately 28 - 30 °C (Fig. 10 C). In 2019, pre-SRE soil temperatures rise without disparities between lagoon and

pond sites. In this case, control lagoon and pond sites (29 - 31 °C) than planted sites (28 - 30 °C) (Fig. 10C).

Post-SRE soil temperatures at lagoon sites remained significantly lower than soil temperature at pond sites in 2017. In 2017, planted and control lagoon pre-SRE soil temperature ranged from approximately 27 - 28 °C, while planted and control pond sites ranged from approximately 28 - 39 °C. Thus, soil temperatures at lagoon and pond sites rose slightly after the SRE apparatus was used when compared to pre-SRE soil temperatures. In 2019, post-SRE soil temperatures at planted lagoon sites increased slightly (28.2 ± 0.8 °C), while control lagoon sites increased (30.8 ± 0.5 °C) in soil temperature after the SRE apparatus was used. At planted pond sites, post-SRE temperatures dropped slightly (28.0 ± 0.8 °C), while soil temperatures at control pond sites increased (30.5 ± 0.4 °C) after the SRE apparatus was utilized (Fig. 10D).

The shoreline slope measurement set:

Table 10 Lagoon and pond planted and control shoreline slope measurements in the beginning and end of sampling period (Q3 – 2017 and Q4 – 2019).

	Lagoon				Pond			
	Planted		Control		Planted		Control	
	2017	2019	2017	2019	2017	2019	2017	2019
Mean	0.10	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.20	0.21	0.21	0.23
Standard Error	0.02	0.05	0.04	0.05	0.08	0.03	0.03	0.03
Median	0.07	0.06	0.09	0.06	0.20	0.21	0.21	0.22
Minimum	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.04	0.03	0.12	0.12	0.17
Maximum	0.20	0.37	0.49	0.37	0.48	0.30	0.30	0.28
Count	10	7	10	7	5	5	5	4

In 2017, the lagoon planted sites displayed a mean slope of 0.10 ± 0.02 , while the control shoreline slope approximated to 0.12 ± 0.04 , respectively. In 2019, both lagoon planted and control sites mean slope approximated to 0.12 ± 0.05 . Shoreline slopes at both pond planted and control sites in 2017 were 0.20 ± 0.08 , and 0.21 ± 0.03 , respectively. In 2019, planted pond sites stayed relatively consistent and approximated to 0.21 ± 0.03 , while the control shoreline slope was 0.23 ± 0.03 .

PUBLIC EDUCATION

The goal of the public education study is to assess the impact of public education on waterfront communities' perception of their roles in contributing to and controlling nonpoint source pollution in an estuarine ecosystem. The study area chosen for this research is within the ML watershed, a sub-lagoon of the IRL. This location was chosen because ML has suffered severe algal blooms since 2011, and is considered an estuary of high significance in the nation. To address the main goal, this project seeks to study two metrics of environmental awareness: the 1) knowledge and 2) behaviors of the lagoon (Mosquito Lagoon) community as they pertain to environmental stewardship.

Materials and Methods

Surveys and outreach activities were conducted in order to (1) assess current knowledge and behaviors of the community in their contribution to nonpoint source pollution; and (2) measure how exposure to public education helps change their knowledge and willingness to change their behaviors. The following three public education methods were used.

Education through guided living shoreline exhibit tour

Living shorelines is a type of shoreline restoration methods using native plants and other organic materials to buffer the amount of nutrients from surface runoff before it enters to a water body. Living shoreline exhibits at the Marine Discovery Center (MDC; 520 Barracuda Blvd., New Smyrna Beach, FL) display native coastal saltmarsh plants and oysters, terraces with native plants, retaining walls with native plants and oysters, seawalls with native plants and oysters, retaining walls with coquina rip rap and native plants, and coquina rip raps with native plants. We have conducted guided exhibit tours for a one-year period to the visitors at MDC to educate various living shorelines to the visitors who attended the exhibit tours. The visitors who chose to participate in the guided tours, if agreed, were given pre- and post-survey questions on general knowledge and their current yard management practices that may affect estuarine water quality. Numbered pre- and post-surveys were given out to protect the confidentiality of people, but to match their pre- and post-survey results. Information given at the guided tour includes the current health of the lagoon, factors that affect the lagoon and drive algal blooms, effects of different types of shorelines including living shorelines on ecosystems, things a waterfront community can do to reduce nonpoint source pollution. A post-survey, with the same types of questions as in the pre-survey, but in a different order, was given at the end of the tour. Hereafter "guided living shoreline exhibit" may be referred to as simply "exhibit(s)."

Education through in-class workshops

In-class workshops were conducted to inform and educate the same information as above and assess their perception of their roles in controlling nonpoint pollution. Workshops were announced through newspaper articles and also through listserv emails sent from the partner organizations such as county libraries, universities, and MDC. Pre- and post-surveys were given out in the same manners as described above. The primary audience for these workshops were the general public living within and around the study area. Hereafter “in-class workshops” may be referred to as simply “workshop(s).”

Education through demonstration at waterfront properties

Owners of residential waterfront properties with their yard/lawn sloping into a water body were recruited within the ML watershed. These residential waterfront properties were selected for environmental education through the living shoreline/water quality assessment demonstration at their properties. Fund from the Environmental Protection Agency allowed free installation of living shorelines and/or water quality/vegetation monitoring at the shoreline on their properties. The property owners were given the pre-survey before the start of the demonstration on their property and the post-survey 6 months after the pre-survey. Surveys for homeowners include the same questions for the surveys given at other education venues in order to compare the three education methods: (1) formal in-class workshop lectures, (2) field guided tours, vs. (3) informal, but personal interactions with homeowners over an extended duration (June-December 2017). Attending an in-class workshop or an exhibit tour was not required for the homeowners. There was a longer lapse time between pre- and post-surveys for the homeowners of about 6 months, whereas the workshop and exhibit tour pre- and post-surveys were done on the same day. Hereafter “waterfront property owners” may be referred to as simply “homeowner(s).”

Survey questions

The survey questions were grouped into two categories: (1) knowledge on the status and controlling factors of the lagoon health; and (2) yard management behavior if they have a yard. The survey data under a same category were grouped together into questions sets (see below) for further analyses in order to compare the pre- and post-surveys, and to show if there are any changes in knowledge or the willingness to change behaviors to help improve the lagoon health (or the actual yard management behaviors by the waterfront property owners). The sets of surveys questions for the two categories, “Knowledge” and “Behavior”, were as follows:

Question Sets: Knowledge Questions

1. Knowledge of the impact that waterfront homes have on the health of the lagoon.
2. Knowledge of the impact that “inland” homes (i.e., > 5 blocks from the lagoon) have on the health of the lagoon.
3. Knowledge of Florida friendly yard management practices and their impacts on the

- lagoon water quality.
4. Knowledge of the differences between natural shorelines vs. armored shorelines.
 5. Benefits of using Florida native plants for waterfront yards as opposed to turf grass.
 6. Types of shorelines that provide the best habitat for wildlife such as waterfowl, juvenile fishes, crabs, and shrimp.
 7. Knowledge on a living shoreline.
 8. Knowledge of the impacts of fertilizers and herbicides applied to a yard have on water runoff into the lagoon.

Question Sets: Behavior Questions (The behavior questions were formulized to address the Volusia County's fertilizer ordinance:

<https://www.volusia.org/core/fileparse.php/5912/urlt/VCFertilizerOrdinance-508.pdf>)

- A. Do you (or your contractor for lawn maintenance) apply fertilizers to the yard?
- B. If yes, how often do you apply them?
- C. Do you apply during the summer (during the banned season)?
- D. Have you applied herbicides to your yard within the last year?
- E. If yes, how often do you apply them?
- F. How often do you mow your yard during summer time?
- G. What type of water do you use to water your yard?
- H. If you water your yard, how frequently do you water your yard?
- I. Do you water on a set schedule or when your yard is in need?

Data Analyses

The survey answers were converted to quantitative measurements for further analyses to compare the survey categories. Each question was scored from 0 to 1, with 0 being least environmentally aware (and/or friendly) and 1 being most environmentally aware (and/or friendly). Higher score values indicate the participant is more environmentally aware and/or would practice environmentally friendly yard maintenance, i.e. adherence to the Volusia County's fertilizer and to the Florida friendly yard management practices campaigned by the Be Floridian Now (<https://befloridiannow.org/>). Missing values or answers with "I don't know" were scored with 0. The questions that had a score of 1 in both pre- and post-surveys were separated from the main statistical analysis as this would give a false zero score (apparent zero gain in environmental awareness).

Descriptive analyses using survey scores were used to gauge current knowledge about the health of the lagoon and to assess the impact of public education on waterfront communities' perception of their roles in contributing to and controlling nonpoint source pollution in the estuarine ecosystem and their willingness to change their behavior.

There are two groups of observations: data sets containing pre and post data; and a data set containing data only from the pre-surveys. Exhibit surveys and workshop surveys contained

behavior data only on the pre-surveys. The difference in pre and post scores was termed the “Change of environmental awareness index” or CEA index. For the sets that did not have post survey data, only the pre-data was analyzed and CEA was not obtained.

To test the effect of education method on the difference between pre and post scores and the components with only pre scores, a series of one-way permutational analysis of variance (perANOVAs) were conducted on each question set with education type as a fixed factor and scaled survey responses as the dependent variable in R using the “aovperm” from the package “permuco v1.0.2” with 99,999 permutations (i.e., lowest possible P-value = 0.00001). Any significant results were further analyzed with a series of pairwise perANOVAs between all paired education types with a Sequential Bonferroni correction as a post-hoc test. To test significant difference between pre- and post-scores, paired permutational t-test were used to detect any significant deviation from 0.

RESULTS

Demographics of public education participants

The number of survey participants for the education methods is the following: 110 for exhibit surveys, 12 for workshop surveys, and 20 for homeowner surveys. Fifty-five out of 110 exhibit survey participants were out-of-town visitors, whereas, 60% of the workshop attendants were homeowners within the study area and lived in the same area for >15 years. Approximately 45% of the homeowners were the residents who have been living at their properties for less than five years. Approximately 80% of the survey participants from all education methods were 45 years old or older. For all education methods combined, 62% were female survey participants, and 38% were male survey participants.

Knowledge change

Understanding of the citizen’s role and impact on local water quality was divided into three categories after assessment: ‘no knowledge gained’, ‘knowledge gained’, and ‘knowledgeable before and after the information was given (being knowledgeable means a score of 1 in the same pre- and post-question).’ Eight question sets were used to assess knowledge, and drawing upon all eight questions, across all education methods combined, 18% of survey participants did not gain any knowledge, 33% of survey participants gained knowledge, and 49% of survey participants had a general knowledge of the health of the ML prior to the education event. Broken down by education method, >50% of the exhibit participants and homeowners were ‘knowledgeable’ before the education event (55% and 53%, respectively; Fig. 1). Exhibits and

workshops showed 38 % and 42% in ‘knowledge gained’, while homeowners had the highest percentage of ‘no knowledge gained’ at 28% (Fig. 11).

Figure 11. Knowledge change for each education method. Differences (in % of the total number of survey participants for each education method) in knowledge gain among the three education types. (Being knowledgeable means a score of 1 for each individual survey question)

At the individual question set level, results of a series of one-way permutational ANOVAs showed that there was a significant difference ($P < 0.05$) in the CEA Index (aka change in knowledge) among the three education methods for 5 of the 8 questions (Question sets 1, 2, 5, 7, 8). And among these questions, overall exhibits and workshops showed greater knowledge gained compared to homeowners ($p < 0.05$).

Yard management behavior

Pre-survey responses to the behavior questions were compared among exhibit, workshop, and homeowner surveys. The results of a series of one-way perANOVAs showed that there was a significant difference in respondent scores among education types for question sets E, F, H and J ($p < 0.05$). And among these questions, homeowners scored intermediate for question set F and lower for question set H, while workshop scored lower for question E but higher for question set F.

With pre and post data, 21% of homeowners implemented some sort of good environmental behavior change (Fig. 12); Good environmental behavior before and after means survey

participants had a score of 1 in the same pre- and post-survey question), and approximately 41% did not change their yard management practices.

Figure 12. Environmental Behavior Index (pre-scores) for the 4 (individual questions G- J, see Section 2.3.5 in methods) across all education methods (Mean \pm SE) are presented. Groups with significantly different Environmental Behavior Index ($P \leq 0.05$ after Sequential Bonferroni correction) are denoted with different lower-case letters.

DISCUSSION

Environmental education can play a vital role in lessening the impact of a problem that can be caused by the community as previous studies agree that the most important outcome of environmental education should be to encourage people in more environmentally friendly behaviors. This research was conducted in order to (1) assess current knowledge and behaviors by the community in their contribution to nonpoint source pollution, and (2) to measure how exposure to public education help change their knowledge and willingness to change their behaviors.

This research used three commonly-conducted public education methods in order to evaluate which is more effective at knowledge gain and assessment in behavior in yard management practices by homeowners, which would help improve environmental quality at the watershed level. The education methods were designed to inform the participants with their roles and actions that can help reduce nutrient input into the ML. This study aimed to see if public education on living shorelines and nonpoint source pollution can change people's knowledge on their roles in the estuarine ecosystem.

Of the workshop survey participants, 42% gained knowledge; 20% did not have a positive change in knowledge (Fig. 11). Also, the exhibit tours turned out to be an effective educational method, as 38% gained knowledge and only 7% did not have a positive change in knowledge (Fig. 11).

Survey participants from exhibit tours were exposed to tangible examples with the education topics, which made them more receptive to the information that was given to them. Previous education studies found that there are many benefits of outdoor experiences, but in-class environmental education is necessary in obtaining structured knowledge in the subject context.

The study participant demographics do not properly represent the regional demographics. For example, there was only one male in workshop surveys, as opposed to the fact 51% of the study area population were male and 49% were female according to the 2014 census data from the City Data. Of all survey participants in this study, 82% were 45 years old or older. A study also had that 73% of participants in her environmental behavior study were above 43 years old. This trend probably was resulted from the time of the workshops and exhibits (during the day time and early evening) so that retired individuals or older homemakers would be more available to attend.

Current environmental awareness from the community in the study area needs improvement. Almost half of survey participants were unaware of the current causes and problems of the ML's health. Knowledge was lacking about ways the community can help to contribute to reducing environmental problems in the lagoon. Environmental education in this research had a positive effect on knowledge change of survey participants, and on environmental behavior change in yard management practices by some homeowners. Active participation and environmental education have been known to improve knowledge gain and awareness of the community about the causes and consequences of environmental issues.

Detailed analyses and results are published in the MS theses and manuscripts (see section Presentations, Publications, and Disseminations).

POST PROJECT MAINTENANCE REPORT AND HOMEOWNER'S FEEDBACK

See attachment "B-CU Living Shorelines Maintenance and Monitoring Report 2021" which was prepared by a contractor, YBE Consulting.

There are also positive spillover impacts at control sites, neighboring locations who requested for possible living shoreline installment after they observed the living shorelines. A homeowner of a control site installed living shorelines at their property and one living shoreline homeowner is planning for additional planting of living shorelines.

CONCLUSION

Surface water TKN, TKP, TSS, Ammonia, Nitrate, or Orthophosphate values were compared among the sites. The surface water sample analyses ensured that the water quality and nutrient values were comparable among the sites (separately analyzed for lagoon sites from pond sites) regardless of the shoreline types (planted living shorelines and turfgrass control sites).

Simulated Rain Event (SRE) water samples were compared to test if there were any differences at nutrients/sediment in the runoff water generated at the planted living shorelines vs. the turfgrass control shores. The SRE data analysis results show that the planted sites had lower TKN and TKP values compared to those at control sites. Compared to the lagoon sites, pond sites exhibited more fluctuating nutrient values between sampling periods.

Assessment of current knowledge and behaviors of the community is important in order to evaluate the knowledge gained following environmental education. The assessment of current knowledge showed that almost half of the survey participants from all education methods were knowledgeable before we conducted the public education. Current behaviors on yard management practices were also assessed for: exhibit survey participants and workshop survey participants, approximately 40% of the participants practice good environmental yard managements. All three education methods, in-class workshop, guided exhibit tour, and informal demonstration at homeowners' backyards, were found to have a positive effect on the knowledge gain of survey participants. In-class workshops surveys were found to have the highest knowledge gain, followed by exhibit survey participants and homeowner survey participants. The informal education also had a positive change in yard management behavior by homeowners. Overall, public education had a positive outcome on knowledge gain and behavior change. Overall, ~30% of participants had a better understanding and perception on their roles in how to contribute to and control nonpoint source pollution in the estuarine ecosystem, and to help improve water quality by implementing environmentally friendly yard management practices.

REFERENCES

- Bellamy, P. and H.J. Cho. 2019. A GIS tool for determining potential runoff coefficient and runoff depth for the Indian River Lagoon, FL. Lagoon Environments Around the World – A Scientific Perspective. IntechOpen. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.87163>.
- Humphry, J. B., Daniel, T. C., Edwards, D. R., & Sharpley, A. N. 2002. A portable rainfall simulator for plot-scale runoff studies. *Applied Engineering in Agriculture*, 18(2), 199.

PRESENTATIONS, PUBLICATIONS, DISSEMINATION

Media Press and Publicity (featuring and acknowledging the project and funding)

- Project film and presentation at the Cinematique Theater November 7, 2020.
- Halifax River Urban Watershed Sustainability Initiative (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RqUMAV2yCQ4&feature=youtu.be>)
- Graduate students and projects featured in In Academia, climate change finds its way into many disciplines. Article in Daytona Beach News Journal (the Rising Seas article series). Oct 7, 2017
- Living Shorelines Lagoon: B-CU project aims to clean up Mosquito Lagoon: Article in Daytona Beach News Journal. Apr 27, 2017
- Research team to discuss water protection efforts: article in Daytona Beach News Journal. Oct 12, 2016
- Bethune-Cookman seeks Southeast Volusia Lawns for Mosquito Lagoon Research: article in Daytona Beach News Journal. Jul 20, 2016
- Lagoon Research: article in Daytona Beach News Journal. Jul 20, 2016

Publications and Theses

- White, M. (defended in November 2021) Analyzing effectiveness of living shorelines in mitigating nonpoint source pollution in urbanized Mosquito Lagoon, Florida.
- Orozco, A., A. Ho, and H.J. Cho. 2020. Evaluation of outreach and public education in raising awareness of waterfront community roles in controlling nonpoint pollution around the Mosquito Lagoon, Florida. International Journal of Energy Water Food Nexus.
- Brooks, M. 2020. Evaluating the Effectiveness of Living Shoreline Buffers in Mitigating Nonpoint Source Pollution and Climate Impacts in the Mosquito Lagoon, Florida, USA. Master's thesis. Bethune-Cookman University, Daytona Beach, FL.
- Orozco, A. 2017. Effect of living shoreline public education and outreach on non-point source pollution into Mosquito Lagoon. Master's thesis. Bethune-Cookman University, Daytona Beach, FL.

Conference Presentations, Public Lectures, and Abstracts (*student)

- White*, M., H.J. Cho, and A. Ho. Analyzing effectiveness of living shorelines in mitigating nonpoint source pollution in urbanized Mosquito Lagoon, FL. 2021 CERF Biennia Conference. Nov 1-4 and 8-11, 2021.
- Cho, H.J. 2021. Aquatic Vegetation Studies and Student Restoration Projects. Save Our Springs and Rivers Academy. Feb. 18, 2021. (Virtual Invited Lecture).
- Cho, H.J. 2020. Lessons learned from employing living shorelines at private waterfront properties. Coastal Habitat Integrated Mapping and Monitoring Workshop 2020. May 12

- 13, 2020. Fish and Wildlife Research Institute, Florida Fish and Wildlife Conservation Commission. St/ Petersburg, FL (Virtual).
- H.J. Cho. 2019. Living shorelines and treatment wetland for stormwater runoff management: Engaging waterfront property owners. Oct 22, 2019. NOAA Atlantic Oceanographic and Meteorological Laboratory (AOML), Miami, FL.
 - Cho, H.J. and A. Ho. 2019. Living Shorelines for the control of nonpoint source pollution along the Mosquito Lagoon. 4/17/2019. The City of Edgewater.
 - Cho, H.J. 2019. Living Shorelines for Stormwater Runoff Management within the Watershed Areas of Mosquito Lagoon and Halifax River. Jan 10, 2019. The Southeast Volusia Audubon Society meeting. Marine Discovery Center, New Smyrna Beach, FL
 - Andrea Orozco*, Adeljean Ho, and H.J. Cho. 2018. Effectiveness of Public Education at Controlling Nonpoint Source Pollution along the Mosquito Lagoon. The 9th Biennial EPP/MSI Forum, March 18-21, 2018. Howard University in Washington, D.C.
 - Mallory Brooks*, Adeljean L. Ho, and Hyun J. Cho. 2018. Evaluating the Effectiveness of Living Shorelines in Mitigating Non-point source Pollution and Increasing Soil Carbon Storage in the Mosquito Lagoon Watershed. The 9th Biennial EPP/MSI Forum, March 18-21, 2018. Howard University in Washington, D.C.
 - Adeljean L. Ho, Abraham Dasilvio, Hyun J. Cho. 2018 Implementing Living Shorelines as Tools For Runoff Treatment & Public Education. The 9th Biennial EPP/MSI Forum, March 18-21, 2018. Howard University in Washington, D.C.
 - Cho, H.J. 2018. Living Shorelines and Wetland Restoration using Florida Native Plants for Stormwater Runoff Management. 2/15/2018. Halifax-Flagler Sierra Club meeting.
 - Cho, H.J. 2018. Recent Costal Resilience Research at Bethune-Cookman’s Environmental Science Program. Feb 26, 2018. Halifax Audubon Society.
 - Andrea Orozco*, Adeljean Ho, and H.J. Cho. 2018. Effectiveness of Public Education at Controlling Nonpoint Source Pollution along the Mosquito Lagoon. Indian River Lagoon Symposium 2018, Feb 8-9. 2018, Harbor Branch Oceanographic Institute at Florida Atlantic University
 - Mallory Brooks*, Adeljean L. Ho, and Hyun J. Cho. 2018. Evaluating the Effectiveness of Living Shorelines in Mitigating Non-point source Pollution and Increasing Soil Carbon Storage in the Mosquito Lagoon Watershed. Indian River Lagoon Symposium 2018, Feb 8-9. 2018, Harbor Branch Oceanographic Institute at Florida Atlantic University
 - Andrea Orozco*, Mallory Brooks*, Adeljean Ho, and H.J. Cho. Converting Non-natives to Living Shorelines to Control Nonpoint Pollution and used as a Tool for Public education, the 41st Annual Florida Aquatic Plant Management Society Conference, Lake Buena Vista, FL. Oct 16 – 19th, 2017. (student travel awarded by the society).
 - Orozco, A. Ho, A.L.F.C., and H.J. Cho. 2017. Living Shorelines for the Control of Nonpoint-Source Pollution along the Mosquito Lagoon. May 11, 2017. New Smyrna Beach Regional Library, New Smyrna Beach, FL
 - Ho, A.L.F.C., A. Orozco, P. Bellamy, and H.J. Cho. 2017. Living shorelines as tools for citizen science and runoff mitigation. 2017 Indian River Lagoon Symposium. Feb 9-10, 2017. Harbor Branch Oceanographic Institute at Florida Atlantic University
 - Orozco, A., H.J. Cho, A. Ho, and P. Bellamy. 2017 Effectiveness of Public Education at

Controlling Nonpoint Source Pollution along the Indian River Lagoon. 2017 Indian River Lagoon Symposium. Feb 9-10, 2017. Harbor Branch Oceanographic Institute at Florida Atlantic University

- Brooks, M, S. Guruvadoo, and H.J. Cho. 2017. Living shorelines as tools for citizen science and runoff mitigation. Jan 13, 2017. NOAA OAR Pacific Marine Ecosystem Laboratory meeting, Portland, Oregon
- Cho, H.J. 2017. Mosquito Lagoon Living shoreline Project using Florida Native Plants. Paw Paw Chapter meeting of Florida Native Plant Society. Jan 9, 2017. Daytona Beach
- Philip Bellamy*, Andrea Orozco*, and H.J. Cho. 2016. Living Shorelines to Control Nonpoint Source Pollution and as a Tool for Public Education along the Mosquito Lagoon. The 51st Annual Water Resources Conference, November 13-17, 2016, Orlando, FL
- Cho, H.J. Water Resources and Living shoreline. Oct 13, 2016. New Smyrna Beach Library
- Cho, H.J. 2016. Water resources and quality of Mosquito Lagoon. 11/17/2016. New Smyrna Beach Library, New Smyrna Beach, FL
- Andrea Orozco and H.J. Cho. 2016. Effectiveness of Living Shorelines at Controlling Nonpoint Source Pollution and as a Tool for Public Education along the Mosquito Lagoon. . Marine Discovery Center Monthly Lecture Focuses On IRL Water Quality. Thursday, June 16, 2016. Marine Discovery Center, New Smyrna Beach, FL.
- Orozco*, A. and H.J. Cho. 2016. Effectiveness of living shorelines at controlling nonpoint source pollution and as a tool for public education along the Mosquito Lagoon. 2016 Bethune-Cookman University Academic Showcase. April 8, 2016. Performing Arts Center, Bethune-Cookman University.